

A machine learning based tool for predicting geometry-induced wrinkles in fabric preforming

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Motivation

- Wrinkling simulations using FE are accurate but not practical for optimisation
- Deep learning models can be accurate with low computational cost
- The effect of tool geometry on wrinkling behaviour is not well understood

Aims

- Develop a deep learning model to predict wrinkling for a range of geometries
- Investigate the relationship between tool geometry and wrinkling

Outline

- Motivation and Aims
- Material and Process
- Method
 - Data Generation
 - Data Pre-processing
 - Surrogate Model
- Results
 - Effect of Tool Geometry
 - Model Performance
 - Computational Cost
- Conclusions and Future Work

Material, Layup & Process

Material
Hexcel `FCIM359`
Biaxial carbon NCF
 $\pm 45^\circ$, pillar stitch

Layup: $[0^\circ/90^\circ, 0^\circ/90^\circ]$, stitch along 45°

Forming Process: Double diaphragm forming

Method Outline

Data Generation

Geometry Generator

1802 Tool Geometries

FE Forming Simulation

Yu et al. (2021)

Geometry Characterisation

Conicity

Area Ratio

Volume Ratio

Tortuosity

Angularity

Mean
Curvature

Gauss
Curvature

Asymmetry

Data Pre-Processing

- Bridging excluded from wrinkle amplitude calculation

Deep Learning Surrogate Model

Effect of Tool Geometry on Wrinkling

By NCF ply in layup

- $[0^\circ/90^\circ, 0^\circ/90^\circ]$ - two NCF layup
- Similar effect for both plies

By NCF shear region

- Asymmetric shear behaviour due to stitch along shearing direction
- Different wrinkling modes in each region
 - Shear (NS) vs lateral compression (PS)

- Note: probability density distributions based on all 1802 simulated tool geometries

Effect of Tool Geometry - Correlation

- Evaluation of correlation between geometry characteristics and wrinkle severity

Conicity

Gauss Curvature

Angularity

- Strong correlation

- Weak correlation

- No correlation

Model Performance – Test Set

- Test set: 186 geometries
- Not previously seen by surrogate model
- Mean wrinkle amplitudes from deep learning surrogate model correlate well with FE predictions

Model Performance – Evaluation Set

Wrinkle Severity

- Significant effect of geometry on wrinkle amplitude

Model Wrinkle Prediction Error

- Reasonable prediction accuracy
- Extrapolation capability limited

Evaluation Geometries

Model Computational Cost

Prediction cost (FE vs DL surrogate model)

<i>Model Type</i>	<i>Computational Cost/hours</i>
Macroscale FE Model	1.33
Pre-trained Surrogate Model	0.000215 (0.7s)

DL surrogate model development computational cost (hours)

Surrogate Model Development	1308
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Conclusions & Future Work

Conclusions

- The effect of tool geometry on wrinkling severity is significant
- Greater tapering → less severe wrinkling
- DL surrogate model can predict fabric wrinkling behaviour during forming
- Surrogate model = approx. 6000x faster than FE model
- Development cost can be further reduced

Conclusions & Future Work

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Future Work

- Numerical variability of wrinkle patterns
- Optimisation of a case study geometry
- Transfer learning to improve extrapolation
- Extension to industrially relevant geometries